

MEASUREMENT OF SURFACE ENERGY OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBRES USING A CAPILLARY INTRUSION METHOD

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1. Introduction

Recycling carbon fibre from carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) has been investigated for almost 20 years driven by landfill legislation, the potential market for recycled fibre and the desire for sustainable manufacturing processes and products. Also, increasing growth in the use of CFRP in aircraft [1] and even automobiles to improve fuel economy makes the recycling very attractive. Recently, commercial companies have emerged to recycle carbon fibres, such as Recycling Carbon Fibre Ltd (RCF Ltd, UK) and Materials Innovation Technologies (US).

The methodology for carbon fibre recycling is to remove the matrix thermoset polymer in the form of small molecules, leaving carbon fibre. To date, there are generally three routes, pyrolysis of the CFRP in the absence of oxygen and then oxidation of the char to release carbon fibre [2], thermo-oxidative processing of CFRP in a fluidised bed to convert thermoset matrix polymer into gaseous products and to blow out the released carbon fibre [3], solvolysis of the thermoset matrix in nitric acid [4] or supercritical fluid [5] to convert the matrix into liquid products and release carbon fibre. All these processes can produce clean carbon fibres, but the recycled fibre is in a short fluffy form because there is no size on the surface of the fibre (as shown in Fig. 1), which makes the application of the recycled carbon fibre problematic [6].

At University of Nottingham, we are developing methodology for evaluation of the performance of recycled carbon fibres in polymer composites. Surface energy is an important parameter for the use of recycled carbon fibres, since it determines the wettability of the fibre and interfacial bonding between fibre and matrix.

Fig. 1. Carbon fibre (T800S) using pyrolysis process from RCF Ltd (UK)

In the measurement of surface energy of a solid, the contact angles of the solid with several probing liquids are determined first, and then various theories can be used to calculate the surface energy of the solid using the known values of the surface tension of the probing liquids [7]. Since carbon fibre has only a diameter of about 7 μm , unlike plate materials, the direct measurement of contact angle with a probe liquid is rather difficult and three indirect methods have reported. The first is the micro-Wilhelmy method [8]. In this method, a single fibre sample is suspended from a microbalance with a precision of at least 0.1 μN , and then the force acting on the fibre sample is measured when the sample is immersed into the probing liquids. The second is the droplet shape method, in which a droplet of the probing liquids is applied on a single fibre and the drop length and height is measured to derive the contact angle using a secondary differential equation for the droplet profile [9-11]. The third is inverse gas chromatography (IGC), in which the fibre is packed into a glass column and then the column is connected to a gas

chromatograph to measure the residence time of probe liquids so that the surface energy can be calculated [12].

The first two methods involve single fibres and the measurement of its diameter. Due to the heterogeneity and irregular shape of carbon fibres, an assumption of circular profile is often used for calculation of the contact angles. Furthermore, expensive instruments such as gas chromatograph or microbalance have to be used. To this end, a capillary intrusion method has been developed to measure the contact angle of recycled carbon fibres with probing liquids.

The capillary intrusion method has widely been used for measuring the contact angles of powder solids with liquids using a modified Washburn method [13]. In this technique, a cylindrical tube is filled with the powder to form a bed, and then the probing liquid rises along the capillary between the particles. The relationship between the mass of the adsorbed liquid (m) and the intrusion time (t) is shown in Eq.1. [14]

$$m^2 = \left(\frac{\rho^2 \gamma c}{\eta} \cos \theta \right) t \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the density, γ is the surface tension and η is the viscosity of the liquid, θ is the contact angle of the liquid with the solid, and c an equivalent of capillary radius.

For recycled carbon fibre, it is difficult to form a bed with the same c each time, which is essential for the capillary intrusion method, due to its fluffy form. We report here a method to overcome this difficulty and then to measure the surface energy of recycled carbon fibres.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Three types of carbon fibre were used in this work: recycled T800S (RCF Ltd) recycled using pyrolysis route, recycled T600S recycled using thermo-oxidative route in a fluidised bed. A virgin T700SC-12000-50C with known surface energy reported in the literature was also used in order to compare the capillary intrusion method used in this work with other methods. Virgin T800S was not used because of its unavailability.

Four probing liquids (with known surface tension) were used: n-heptane (used as a complete wetting

liquid, $\theta = 0^\circ$); ethylene glycol, formamide, and distilled water. The first three liquids were from Sigma-Aldrich without further purification.

2.2 Method

The fluffy recycled carbon fibre (Fig. 1) was first dispersed uniformly in glycerol using a kitchen blender. A wet-laid process was then used to transform it into a random mat with an areal density of about 200 g/m^2 , as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. A random mat made from recycled carbon fibre (recycled T800S from RCF Ltd)

A piece of $40 \times 85 \text{ mm}$ was cut as testing sample for sorption experiment. The sample was clamped between two 5 mm thick stainless-steel plates with a 2 mm thick spacer, as illustrated in Fig. 3. A picture of the measurement set-up is shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 3. Experimental set up for the measurement

Fig.4. A picture of the set-up for capillary intrusion method for measurement of surface energy of recycled carbon fibre in a fume cupboard

The bath of probing liquid was placed on one end of a steel plate, which was on the top of a lab jack. The other end of the plate was balanced using a metal block. The metal plate was inserted into a cylinder through a window on its side. The cylinder was placed on a balance, which was connected to a computer to record the mass-time data. The sample was suspended from the top of the cylinder into the bath just above its liquid surface. The bath was then raised until the bottom of the sample just contacted the liquid surface and the liquid began to rise up along the sample due to the capillary force. Raw data were collected automatically at a rate of one point per second. The square of the mass of the probe liquid (m^2) was then plotted against time (t). Linear regression analysis was used to obtain the slope for the straight part of the curve. The slope of the curve in the first 10-30 seconds was used to determine the constant “c” using n-heptane and the constant was then used to calculate the contact angle “ θ ” from the slopes of the other probe liquids.

Three samples were repeated for each probing liquid. The average of three slopes was used to give the constant “c” or contact angle “ θ ”.

After measuring the contact angles of the probing liquids with the carbon fibres, Eq. 2 [14] was used to calculate the surface energy by plotting $\gamma_L(1+\cos\theta)/(2\gamma_L^d)^{0.5}$ against $(\gamma_L^p)^{0.5}/(\gamma_L^d)^{0.5}$ [15]. The slope was the polar component (γ_s^p), and the intercept on y axis was the dispersion component (γ_s^d) of the surface energy of the carbon fibre.

$$\frac{\gamma_L(1+\cos\theta)}{2\sqrt{\gamma_L^d}} = \sqrt{\gamma_s^p} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma_L^p}}{\gamma_L^d} \right) + \sqrt{\gamma_s^d} \quad (2)$$

In the equation, γ is the surface energy, and subscript L liquid, s solid, and the superscript p polar component and d dispersion component of surface energy. The dispersion component is due to the Lifshitz-van der Waals interactions, i.e. interactions between two completely apolar compounds, while the polar component is due to electron acceptor-electron donor interactions, i.e. acid-base interactions [13].

3. Results and discussion

The key step for the use of the capillary intrusion method to determine the contact angle between fluffy recycled carbon fibre with probing liquids is to determine the “c” constant in Eq. 1. This is usually conducted by using a liquid with very low surface tension such as alkanes, assuming that contact angle “ θ ” is equal to zero. In the experiments with other probing liquids, the same “c” was assumed. For a powder sample, it can be poured into a tube and then tapping the same times using a standard instrument to get the same “c” for each probe liquid. However, for fluffy fibres, it is impossible to get the same “c” using this method.

In order to get the same “c”, the fluffy fibre was first transformed into a random mat. Each time, the same size of the mat was cut from the whole piece and then clamped between two steel plates with a 2 mm spacer. To maintain the reproducibility of the constant “c”, the spacer was necessary. Otherwise the thickness would change during liquid uptake. It was found that a bath with wide diameter was better to keep the least change of liquid level during liquid uptake. Another factor to be considered is the thickness of the sample. It was shown that the uptake of the viscous liquid had a low reproducibility when the sample thickness was less than 1 mm. Therefore, the mat was made with an areal density of 200 g/m² and clamped between two steel plates and a 2 mm thick spacer.

The method was first used to measure the surface energy of T700SC carbon fibre. The fibre was cut to 3 mm in length and dispersed using the blender and transformed into a random mat. The plot for calculating surface energy is shown in Fig. 5, and the result for T700SC is shown in Table 1 with a

comparison with the literature reported values, which was measured using micro-Wilhelmy method and IGC method respectively.

Fig.5. The plot for T700SC fibre to calculate the surface energy using Eq. 2

Table 1. Contact angles and surface energy of T700SC-12000-50C fibre obtained in this work and literature values.

	This work	micro-Wilhelmy [16]	IGC [17]
Contact angle ($^{\circ}$)			
<i>Formamide</i>	48.1		
<i>EG</i>	32.4		
<i>Water</i>	73.5	69.4	
Surface energy (mJ/m ²)			
γ_s^d	35.6	31.7	32.7
γ_s^p	7.1	10.3	16.6
γ_s	42.7	42.0	49.3

It can be seen from Table 1 that the capillary intrusion method is comparable with the micro-Wilhelmy method. However, the value was lower than that obtained from IGC method. Both the micro-Wilhelmy method and the capillary intrusion method use the capillary force, but the IGC method uses an acceptor-donor principle. This may be the main reason for the difference.

The method was then used to measure the two recycled carbon fibres. The plots for calculating surface energy are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 respectively for RCF fibre and fluidised bed fibre. The results for surface energy are listed in Table 2 for the two different carbon fibres. The surface

energies of the two recycled carbon fibres are similar at 46 mJ/m². This may be because both recycling processes involve an oxidation stage in air.

Fig. 6. The plot for RCF recycled carbon fibre to calculate the surface energy using Eq. 2

Fig. 7. The plot for fluid bed recycled carbon fibre to calculate the surface energy using Eq. 2

Table 2. Contact angles and surface energy of recycled carbon fibres.

	RCF fibre	Fluid bed fibre
Contact angle ($^{\circ}$)		
<i>Formamide</i>	37.3	30.1
<i>EG</i>	28.8	25.0
<i>Water</i>	55.7	54.2
Surface energy (mJ/m ²)		
γ_s^d	22.0	25.0
γ_s^p	23.8	22.8
γ_s	45.8	47.8

The virgin carbon fibre after surface treatment has a surface energy of 35-50 mJ/m². It can thus be seen that the recycled carbon fibre has a comparable surface energy as that of virgin carbon fibre. This indicates that no further surface treatment may be needed for the use of the recycled carbon fibre from pyrolysis or thermo-oxidative process.

4. Conclusions

In this work, the capillary intrusion method was developed to measure the surface energy of fluffy recycled carbon fibres. By transforming the fluffy recycled carbon fibre into a uniform random mat, a constant “c” parameter can be achieved, which is the key step for the use of capillary intrusion method. The measured surface energies of the recycled carbon fibres from both pyrolysis and thermo-oxidative process in a fluidised bed have similar values of about 46 mJ/m².

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